

What Drives Employee to Innovate and Perform in Manufacture Companies?: The Moderating Role of Organizational Learning Culture

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the effect of team building, employee empowerment, employee self-efficacy on the employee competencies and examine the moderating role of organizational learning culture between these relationship. Further to analyze the direct impact of employee competencies toward innovation and job performance. Using certain criteria, 404 employees of two leading manufacture companies in Indonesia were selected purposively for this quantitative survey study. PLS-SEM approach was deployed to analyze the data collected by questionnaire with Likert scale. Result of the study demonstrated that employee competencies proven has significant effect toward innovation and job performance, meanwhile team building has strongest effect to influence employee competencies following by employee self-efficacy. Organizational learning culture only found to strengthen the influence from self-efficacy. This study could be beneficial to decision makers of manufacturing companies to develop human resources strategies, mainly to improve organizational learning culture that could drive the potential of the employee to the fullest of their potential. There are limitation and suggestion to the further study as well.

Keywords: *Employee Competencies, Innovation, Job Performance, Organizational Learning Culture, Manufacturing Company.*

INTRODUCTION

Innovation and job performance of each employee is the key to success for manufacturing organizations toward volatile, and complex business environment (Matos et al., 2021; Kouty, 2021). To achieve process innovation and optimal job performance, all employees should contribute to the organization. Strategically, employees who have competencies according to their field of work will be benefited for the progress of the organization (Chernova, Chernov & Komarove, 2020), this indeed apply in the manufacturing sector which rely on production process.

Currently, the industry's growth is affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, where almost all the country's economic experienced a negative growth (Matteo & Frederic, 2021). This pandemic unavoidable has an impact on decreasing demand which will affect in downtrend supply from the manufacturing industry (Gu, Domer, & O'Connor, 2021). Meanwhile, there is an increase in operational costs, for example to implement health protocols in factories. Its inevitable, that every industry must innovate to face the new normal challenge (Dwivedi et al., 2021) and adapt to the conditions affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. Company must be able to execute cost reduction and reduce waste, this process should involve all employees in the routine manufacturing process who can provide input and ideas to support the process (Matos et al., 2021). In other words, employees productivity can also be seen from the output of the innovation ability and adoption. In the manufacturing industry, the productivity results of human resources (HR) management are in accordance with the new concept whereas employees are not only seen from the way they carry out the assigned tasks but must be seen from their ability to perform critical thinking, problem solving and creativity (Ngo, Lau, & Foley, 2008). It should be considered that employees are involved in the innovation process, thus through the innovation, efficiency is achieved (Patro, 2020).

Employee competencies is important factor in a manufacturing company (Saniuk & Caganova, 2021). In the manufacturing industry, employee capability is critical in order to compete with the quality (Warren, Roy, & Robinson, 2021). Likewise, competence of the employee has a direct impact on job performance (Rajapathirana & Hui, 2018). Placing employees with the right competencies will bring organizations to achieve competitive advantages (Marczewska, et al, 2020), although employee competencies can be influenced by multi factors. Respective factors that have been identified are team building and employee empowerment (Potnuru, Sahoo, & Sharma, 2019). This well-respected study shows both have a positive significant effect on employee competence. Earlier study from Barba Aragon et al., (2018) argued that to predict employee competence, it is necessary to look at the individual factors concerned. This is based on Bandura's social learning theory that argued rather than only extrinsic factors, there are also intrinsic factors that influence, where people want to learn and develop themselves with full awareness and control within themselves (Bandura, 1995). Human resource studies then use self-efficacy variables to predict intrinsic motives that can effect

employee performance (Mullen & Lambie, 2016; Rahim et al, 2019). Respectively, this study implies self-efficacy as a predictor of employee competencies.

Previous study has identified other variables that can moderate the effect of employee competence derived from organizational interventions on learning aspects. A study from Tedla (2016), shows the role of learning organizational culture which facilitate coaching or training in helping every employee to have competence. Organizational culture also proven to have an effect on the quality of employees (Atan & Mahmood, 2019). However in another study organizational learning culture was found to have no direct effect (Ngo, Lau, & Foley, 2008) this remain as question regarding the role of learning culture in the level of organization. So far, not many studies analyze the organizational learning culture as a moderator, especially in the context of manufacturing companies, particularly how it could strengthen the management practice, in that regard the research questions raised as follows:

RQ1. Does team building, employee empowerment, employee self-efficacy has positif influent on employee competencies?

RQ2. Does organizational learning culture moderate the relationship to employee competencies?

RQ3. Does employee competencies have a direct effect on innovation and job performance?

This study proposes a new model that modifies the previous studies, which will be empirically tested on employees of manufacturing companies in Indonesia during pandemic of Covid-19 in year of 2021. Indonesia as emerging country still rely the economic growth on the manufacturing sectors, thus make the study relevant. This research model was developed to answer the 3 research questions (RQ) above, where employee competencies was deploy as mediating variable, and organizational learning culture as moderating variable in the research model. This research is expected to contribute to the body of knowledge of HR Management by investigate, how the organizational learning culture can strengthen the influence of team building, employee empowerment and self-efficacy. The results of this study can be beneficial to support HR in manufacturing companies develop program effectively during downtime caused by pandemic Covid-19.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Theoretical Background

Employees are critical to the organizational success (Noe et al., 2015), especially who have high competence align with the organizational objective. Employee competence according to (Spencer & Spencer, 1993) is a characteristic that underlies a person related to the effectiveness of employee performance in completing his work in certain situations. Jackson, Peacock, and Holden (1982) states that the term competence has been used to describe the attributes needed to produce effective performance. Employee competencies strongly influenced by the organizational learning culture of each company according to Senge (1991). Thus this research adapt that definition stated organizational learning culture is an organization where people in it over time continue to develop their capacity to get the results they expect, and people continue to learn.

The competence of an employee in an organization is strongly influenced by several extrinsic factors, such as team building and employee empowerment. However, over time, extrinsic factors alone are not enough to predict employee competence (Banerjee, et al., 2016). There are also intrinsic factors that need to be explored by organizations, such as employee self-efficacy (Jamil & Mahmud, 2019). Self-efficacy not only known as the attitudes of employees but also the skills possessed by each employee. In accordance with research by Aguinis and Edwards (2014), when employee performance is in line with organizational goals, the organization will gain a competitive advantage. This is related to the most important HR function that placing employees in the right position could maximize innovation and performance, so the organization fulfill its strategic goals (Johanson & Vahlne, 2009).

Team Building

Team Building involves the process of enabling a group of people to achieve their goals. It consists of steps such as clarification of team goals, identification of obstacles to goal achievement, address the identified challenges, and enable the achievement of objectives (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009). Moreover, Fajana et al., (2002) asserts that teamwork is the integration of resources and inputs that work in harmony to achieve organizational goals, where roles are determined for each member of the organization, the challenges faced are the same and gradually. According to Cleland (2009), team building is a process of forming, growing, and improving the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of individuals with different needs, backgrounds, and abilities into one integrated and high-performing team.

In previous research by Sulaiman et al., (2012) team building has a positive effect on employee competencies in an organization. This is in line with research done by Tinuke (2013) where team building does not only mean uniting teams but generate the competency. The perspective of the competency is more than a generic activity but imposed on a team

through the consideration for what the team wants or needs to achieve optimal employee competencies. The results of those studies are also confirmed by Potnuru et al., (2019) where team building significantly affects the competence of employees in an organization. On this basis, in this study, it is hypothesized as follows: H1: Team building has positive effect to employee competencies

Employee Empowerment

Empowering Employees in a collaborative environment by giving employees the means, capabilities, and control authority to do things. It involves trying to take full advantage of the organization's human resources by giving everyone more information and control over how they do their jobs (Díaz-Fernández et al., 2013). Various empowerment techniques range from participation in decision making to the use of self-managed or empowered teams in organization.

Employee empowerment is the process of sharing power with employees, thereby increasing their confidence in their ability to do their jobs and their belief that they are influential contributors to the organization. Thomas and Velthouse (1990) were proposed a second perspective on empowerment, defining empowerment in terms of the concepts of cognitive motivation or psychological empowerment. The following definition is consistent with psychological concepts, for example David (1987) views empowerment as a motivational construct. He asserts that, in the context of work, empowerment fulfills the role of freeing a person from tight control with instructions, policies, and orders, and giving that person the freedom to take responsibility for ideas, decisions, and actions. Employee empowerment is influential element to the employee competencies, consequently it could hypothesize as follow: H2: Employee empowerment has positive effects to employee competencies.

Employee Self Efficacy

Employee self-efficacy refers to each employee's belief in his or her capacity to perform the behaviors necessary to produce certain performance achievements (Bandura, 1995). Self-efficacy reflects a belief in one's ability to exercise control over one's motivation, behavior, and social environment. That may apply in the manufacturing employee. This cognitive self-evaluation according to Bandura (1995), affects all kinds of employee experiences, including the goals people strive for, the amount of energy expended in achieving the goals, and the likelihood of achieving a certain level of behavioral performance.

Mahmud et al., (2014) argues that employee self-efficacy is the ability of employees to determine the necessary effective actions that are in accordance with environmental needs, using various resources that are able to move their motivation. Similarly, according to study by Mullen and Lambie (2016) the efficacy of motivating employees is related to how they think, feel, and act. This study demonstrated that self-efficacy is significantly related to the work attitudes, training abilities and is able to improve employee and organizational performance. Furthermore Johnson et al., (2013) revealed that a high level of self-efficacy, strongly affect learning attitudes, thus address the importance of development programs tailored for each employees. The maturity of this self-efficacy will greatly affect the competence of employees therefore it could be hypothesize as follow: H3: Employee self-efficacy has positive effect to employee competencies

Organizational Learning Culture

In particular, organizational learning culture (OLC) allows individuals to learn from each other which is liberating for the creation of creative ideas and transfer of knowledge (Choi, 2019). The purpose of building an organizational learning culture is to expand people's capacity to create the results they really want, new and expansive employee mindsets to be encouraged, collective aspirations to be liberated, and employers must continually learn how to learn together (Senge, 1991). Organizational learning culture can be classified as a condition that allows organizations to adapt to changes in the environment to win the business competition (Denison, 2004). Competitive advantage in companies comes from the support of organizational learning culture as argued by Kotter and Heskett (2011) earlier of that, Jackson & Schuler (1995) stated that organizational culture and human resource management cannot be separated in an organization. Organizational learning culture is partly shaped by human resource management systems and further organizational learning culture proven has positive effect on employee performance (Ngo et al., 2008).

Empirically, previous research (Ngo et al., 2008; Roy et al., 2016) revealed that the dimensions of human resources simultaneously have a positive and significant relationship to organization cultural adaptation. The organization adaptation is most relevant to the flexibility of human resources. In the long run, this culture could help organizations to anticipate and adapt to environmental changes in order to win the competition (Denison, 2004; Kotter & Heskett, 1992). Research by Potnuru et al., (2019) revealed that adaptation of organizational learning culture has a significant positive impact on employee competencies through team building and employee empowerment. In the other side, employees who have worked for more than years and earned certain position in company tend to gain self-efficacy. Further, the relationship between employee self-efficacy and competencies will be investigated and the following hypothesis proposed:

H4: Organizational learning culture strengthen the effect between team building on employee competencies.

H5: Organizational learning culture strengthen the effect between employee empowerment on employee competencies.

H6: Organizational learning culture strengthen the effect between employee self-efficacy on employee competencies.

Employee Competencies

Competence is a person's underlying characteristics that are causally related to the benchmark criteria for effective performance and or excelling in work (Zaim et al., 2013; Eldridge & McCourt, 2011), where competence is a characteristic of a person's ability that can be proven to produce job performance. This was further developed by Eldridge & McCourt (2011) who stated that the term competence has been used to describe the attributes needed to produce effective job performance and innovation in manufacturing organizations. Analyze the effect of employee competence on performance in manufacturing companies in Indonesia. Competence is a basic characteristic possessed by an individual that is causally related to the fulfillment of the criteria needed to occupy a position and contains aspects of knowledge, skills, or personality characteristics that can affect performance (Spencer & Spencer, 1993; Becker et al., 2001). Competence and employee performance have a positive and significant relationship to innovation (Ismail & Abidin, 2010). Employees must have high competence that is able to respond to changes in the business environment so that it has an impact on improving performance. The results of the study (Ismail and Abidin, 2010) showed that employee competence has a significant effect on employee performance. This is in accordance with the argumen by (Spencer and Spencer, 1993) which states that competence can affect employee performance, moreover employee competencies can have a positive impact on employee adaptation to dynamic business changes to absorb innovation more quickly and easily.

Innovation

Innovation generates and implements new processes, products, and ideas (Albros-Garrigos, 2009), in the other hand, Droge et al., (2010) stated that innovation uses applied the same model as in the manufacturing sector, without affecting the characteristics of innovation in services sectors. The current study expands their grouping and identifies indicators that directly or indirectly influence the success of an innovation. Success is considered as the successful commercialization of innovation in terms of a high level of sales (Astebro & Bernhardt, 2005). The direct indicators are the percentage of ideas found to be available for commercialization (Dewangan & Godse, 2014) however innovation in the production process such in manufacture company is rely upon the process innovation (Astebro & Bernhardt, 2005). Therefore, this study considere innovation as efficiency in reducing waist circumference, reducing defects, and reducing cost reductions.

Job Performance

Every employee will always crave the results of his work which is closely related to proper and fair rewards. Bittencourt et al., (2004) underlined that work performance is the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out his duties. The performance appraisal needs to be done on an objective basis because it will be a motivation and reference for employees in their daily work. Champbell (1990) pointed the measurable actions and outcomes that employees engage or bring about that are related to and contribute to organizational goals. In this study, performance refer to the real behavior displayed by each employee as job performance produced by employees according to their role in the organization (Bayram-Arli, 2018). Job performance is include quality, quantity, attendance, and the ability to work together in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to particular employee. Consider those studies the below hypotheses could be proposed:

H7: Employee competencies has positive effect to innovation

H8: Employee competencies has positive effect to job performance

Based on the eight hypotheses above, the conceptual framework of this study can be drawn as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

To carry out this research, a quantitative with a survey approach was used to measure the relationship of seven constructs consisting of team building, employee empowerment, employee self-efficacy, learning organizational culture, employee competence, innovation, and job performance. The population of this research is from the supervisor to above level from various departments in two leading large manufacturing companies in Indonesia that have establish learning culture. Manufacturing employees were chosen purposively as respondents from two companies, the first 204 respondents from a company as the largest battery manufacturer in Indonesia. The second 200 respondent from a company engaged in the manufacture of snacks. Data collection was obtained by purposive sampling with certain criteria, such as permanent employee were included in this study. According to Kock and Hadaya (2016) the minimum samples for PLS-SEM is 160 to meet the statistical power. This study uses total of 404 respondents, thus the minimum sample requirements are met. Data collection taken in June 2021, during the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia, through a structured questionnaire instrument. The questionnaire distributed online to the list of respondent with the assistance of the human resources department in the company to ensure the questionnaire well distributed to the targeted respondents.

The measurement of the construct in this study was developed by the previous studies with instrument based on a Likert scale 1-6, where scale 1 represent not agree at all, to scale 6 that represent strongly agree. The team building questions item consists of five questions adapted from related studies (Aga et al., 2016; Salas et al., 1999). The employee empowerment measurement instrument consists of three question items adapted from Menon, (2001) modified by Menand Stacks (2013). The question items for employee self-efficacy consists of six questions adopted from Warren et al., (2021), there are four questions for organizational learning culture variables adopted from Yang et al., (2004). There are eight instruments from Diaz-Fernandez et al.(2015) that were taken to measure the employee competencies variable, while for the innovation there were three questions instruments adopted from Marsick & Watkins (2003) and there were six questions measuring instruments for the job performance variable from Gu et al., (2021).

To answer the research questions in this study, data analysis were done by Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). According to Hair et al., (2019), PLS is a variance-based structural equation model (SEM), as part of a statistical study that can test a series of relationships simultaneously. PLS-SEM is appropriate due to the objective of this study is an explanatory and predictive, more over if the research model is complex (Hair et al., 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2017). In this study, the SmartPLS® 3.3.3 software was used with bootstrapping approach to test the hypotheses (Memon et al., 2021), According to Ringle and Sarstedt (2016) SmartPLS® performs two stages of evaluation, firstly the outer model to test the reliability and validity, Secondly the inner model to evaluate the structural relationship, including to the test the hypothesis based on the significance and coefficients.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The respond from the distribution of the questionnaire obtained 200 and 204 eligible respondents from the two manufacturing companies. A total of 404 respondents whose profiles are described in Table 1. From the 404

respondents who participated in this survey, most of them are under 40 years old (56.96%), earned a bachelor's degree (50.24%) which indicate that respondents are consider as young and well educated. The length of work in particular company is of 6-10 years (36.13%), so it can be said that employees are quite familiar with the organizational culture. The level of respondents position is dominated by managerial assistant up to general manager positions (67.57%) while the level of supervisors and assistant supervisor 32.43%. This respondent's profile is relevant to the purpose of this study to analyze competencies and job performance in manufacturing companies.

Table 1. Respodent Profile

DemographicVariable		Sample (n)	Percentage(%)
Gender	Male	308	76,23
	Female	96	23,77
Age	<20 years	0	0
	21-30 years	64	15,85
	31-40 years	166	41,08
	41-50 years	153	37,88
	51-60 years	21	5,19
Education	MiddleSchool	0	0
	HighSchool	54	13,38
	Diploma	61	15,09
	Bachelor	203	50,24
	Magister	66	16,34
	Doctoral	20	4,95
LengthofWork	<1 year	30	7,43
	1-5 years	97	24,02
	6-10 years	146	36,13
	>10 years	131	32,42
Position	AssistantSupervisor	74	18,32
	Supervisor	57	14,11
	AssistantManager	93	23,02
	Manager	112	27,72
	General Manager	68	16,83

Measurement model (outer model) assessment is carried out to test the reliability and validity of the variable indicators in the research model. Prior to the assessment of the relationship between constructs, all data had met the criteria of validity and reliability in the analysis of the PLS-SEM measurement model.

Table 2. Construct Reliability and Validity

VARIABLE & INDICATORS	Outer Loading	CA	CR	AVE
Employee Competencies				
EC1: I am always motivated to excel.	0,829	0,928	0,941	0,669
EC2: I feel confident in my competence.	0,811			
EC3: I am able to control myself under pressure.	0,899			
EC4: I was able to survive the difficult conditions within the organization.	0,773			
EC5: I am able to order work according to work priority.	0,812			
EC6: I always exchange ideas with co-workers about work.	0,864			
EC7: I always work without waiting for orders from superiors.	0,706			
EC8: I always take the time to find the latest information on various things.	0,834			
Employee Empowerment				
EE1: Every employee is involved in the decision-making process in various forums.	0,896	0,928	0,930	0,815
EE2: Accessibility to Company information and resources needs to be done in a better way.	0,871			
EE3: Every Employee can participate in the planning and scheduling of daily activities.	0,940			
Innovation				
I1 : I am able to find new ways of working.	0,921	0,896	0,935	0,828
I2 : I have the ability to continuously improve my work by finding new ways within the team.	0,892			
I3 : I will quickly respond in response to changing needs within the company I work for.	0,917			
Job Performance				
JP1: I am able to complete work according to the quality standards set.	0,900	0,939	0,951	0,765

JP2: I am able to complete the quantity/amount of work set by the Company.	0,857			
JP3: I am able to complete work efficiently.	0,885			
JP4: I am able to complete work effectively.	0,844			
JP5: I am able to complete the work assigned by the Company on time.	0,888			
JP6: I feel I have contributed to the company.	0,874			
Organizational Learning Culture				
OLC1: The company always provides work direction to every employee.	0,860	0,843	0,895	0,681
OLC2: The company provides training to increase the working knowledge of its employees.	0,837			
OLC3: Employees who excel are awarded by the Company.	0,775			
OLC4: The company always responds when there are complaints from employees.	0,825			
Employee Self Efficacy				
ESE1: I feel experienced in my work.	0,831	0,913	0,932	0,695
ESE2: No technical problems related to my skills when working.	0,842			
ESE3: I feel clear about the tasks my boss has given me.	0,858			
ESE4: I am still enthusiastic about working even without supervision from my superiors.	0,832			
ESE5: I feel familiar with the products produced by the Company.	0,824			
ESE6: I always try hard to achieve good work results	0,814			
Team Building				
TB1: All team members have complete skills to complete their work tasks within the team	0,841	0,875	0,909	0,668
TB2: In team work using effective strategies.	0,885			
TB3: Each team member knows each other's job roles and responsibilities.	0,827			
TB4: Every team member communicates well with each other.	0,803			
TB5: Each member on the team has a significant influence on decisions that affect team performance.	0,723			

Table 2. shows that all indicators have an outer loading > 0.708 as required, with Cronbach alpha and composite reliability greater than 0,7 which indicates that the internal consistency of the construction is reliable. The AVE measures convergent validity checks, where all values have an AVE ≥ 0.50, indicating that all constructs explain at least 50 percent of item variance and therefore establish validity (Hair et al., 2019).

To test the discriminant validity, the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HT/MT) was deployed since this method known has more precise value (Hair et al., 2019) refer to Henseller, et al., 2014) the recommended threshold value is 0.85 to establish each construct indicator are conceptually different. Table 3 (HT/MT Ratio) shows that all HT/MT values are well below the 0.85 thresholds for all variables. Thus, its concluded that all indicators used in this research model have adequat discrimination to measure their respective constructs.

Table 3. HT/MT Ratio

Variables	EC	EE	ESE	I	JP	Mod effect for OLC to EE	Mod effect for OLC to ESE	Mod effect for OLC to TB	OLC	TB
EC										
EE	0,607									
ESE	0,779	0,509								
I	0,590	0,850	0,550							
JP	0,552	0,538	0,488	0,506						
Mod effect for OLC to EE	0,309	0,000	0,307	0,039	0,183					
Mod effect for OLC to ESE	0,162	0,259	0,000	0,155	0,154	0,690				
Mod effect for OLC to TB	0,221	0,087	0,186	0,115	0,128	0,714	0,601			
OLC	0,808	0,622	0,730	0,561	0,529	0,000	0,000	0,000		

TB	0,791	0,674	0,701	0,583	0,586	0,237	0,209	0,000	0,764
OLC	: Organizational Learning Culture				EE	: Employee Empowerment			
TB	: Team Building				I	: Innovation			
ESE	: Employee Self Efficacy				JP	: Job Performance			
EC	: Employee Competencies								

As a conclusion from the assessment of the outer model analysis, all indicators in the model are reliable and valid to measure their respective constructs specifically, therefore it could proceed to inner model evaluation. Structural model assessment (inner model) was conducted to evaluate the relationship of the variables in the model. The first part in assessment is Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to check the multi-collinearity issue (Sarstedh et al., 2017). The inner VIF value in this model shows that all are below 3, indicating there is no collinearity problem of the constructs in model.

Since goodness of fit was not used in PLS-SEM as suggested by Hair et al., (2019) this study performed R² to measure prediction accuracy and cross redundancy value of Q² to measure the predictive relevance of test model. Employee competence has R² = 0.720 and Q² = 0.472, indicating this construct has strong predictive accuracy and that employee competence could be explained around 72% by variables in the model. Meanwhile, innovation (R² = 0.290; Q² = 0.238), and job performance (R² = 0.273; Q² = 0.263) have moderate predictive accuracy (Hair et al., 2019). This result may associate to the number of prediction path to the dependent variable that are only represent by single path, therefore it should also consider the f² value which shown the f² greater than 0,35 thus could be said has large effect toward both innovation and job performance.

Hypothesis testing by bootstrap procedure was conducted to determine the effect of the variables and determine whether the hypothesis proposed by this study was supported. The bootstrap approach is used to establish the significance of the data (Memon, et al., 2021) The cut-off value of T-statistic > 1.645 (one-tailed) with alpha 0,05 was used as a criterion to determine whether the hypothesis supported or not. The results are shown in Table 4. In addition, mediation analysis was also carried out to determine the mediation significance, through the specific indirect effects as recommend by Nitzlet et al., (2016).

Table 4. Significant and Coefficient

Hypothesis	Standardized Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Values	Result
H1: Team Building → Employee Competencies	0,261	2,964	0,002	Hypothesis Supported
H2: Employee Empowerment → Employee Competencies	0,159	2,773	0,003	Hypothesis Supported
H3: Employee Self Efficacy → Employee Competencies	0,178	2,406	0,008	Hypothesis Supported
H4: Moderating effect for Organizational Learning Culture to Team Building → Employee Competencies	-0,096	1,468*	0,071	Hypothesis Not Supported
H5: Moderating effect for Organizational Learning Culture to Employee Empowerment → Employee Competencies	-0,194	2,810	0,003	Hypothesis Not Supported
H6: Moderating effect for Organizational Learning Culture to Employee Self Efficacy → Employee Competencies	0,143	2,311	0,011	Hypothesis Supported
H7: Employee Competencies → Innovation	0,539	10,027	0,000	Hypothesis Supported
H8: Employee Competencies → Job Performance	0,523	9,749	0,000	Hypothesis Supported

*Not significant

It could be seen in Table 4, out of the 8 proposed hypotheses, 6 are supported by a T-statistic >1.645, a P-value <0.05, with the positive direction as seen in standardized coefficient. For H4, T-statistic was found <1.645 and P-value >0.05, hence, it can be concluded that OLC has no significant effect on moderating team building toward the formation of employee competencies. Meanwhile for H6, the relation of the organizational learning culture as moderator for self-efficacy, the T-statistic is 2,810, P-value <0.05, with the positive coefficient 0,143 hence, it could be concluded that hypothesis is supported. For H5, the T-statistic found >1.645 and P-value <0.05, however it has negative direction that against the directional hypothesis, therefore even OLC has significant effect on employee empowerment but the hypothesis could not supported. This may relate to the profile of respondent level in organization structure, nevertheless, this negative effect which weakening the relationship remain to be analyzed in more deeply.

Table 5. Specific Indirect Effect

Path	Standardized Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Value
Team Building → Employee Competencies → Innovation	0,047	2,975	0,002
Team Building → Employee Competencies → Job Performance	0,047	2,873	0,002
Employee Empowerment → Employee Competencies → Innovation	0,036	2,396	0,008
Employee Empowerment → Employee Competencies → Job Performance	0,033	2,553	0,005

Self-efficacy → Employee Competencies → Innovation	0,041	2,352	0,010
Self-efficacy → Employee Competencies → Job Performance	0,040	2,355	0,009

Based on the mediation analysis (Table 5), the employee competency as mediator construct tested had a T-Statistic above 1,645 and P-value below the 0.05 threshold, which indicates that the mediator's role of employee competencies is proven significant. All the paths show significant values, thus it can be concluded that employee competencies are effective to mediate partially all independent variables, while the strongest mediating effect is seen in the link of team building toward innovation and job performance as well.

Performance-performance map analysis (IPMA) provides management with insight into which areas are more important for target constructs (Hair, et al., 2019) and could help managers to identify priority for improvement based on indicators' performance (mean) and importance (total effect) evaluation.

Figure 2. IPMA indicator of innovation construct

The selected targets for IPMA are innovation and job performance as dependent variables. Figure 2 explains that employee competencies are important constructs for innovation, with specific indicators namely EC6, EC3, and EC8 (“I always exchange ideas with co-workers about work”, “I am able to control my self under pressure”, “I always take the time to find the latest information on various things.”), IPMA is also used to assess the most important indicators based on employees' perspective.

Figure 3. IPMA indicator of job performance construct

Figure 3 explains that employee competencies are important constructs on job performance, namely EC3, EC6, and EC8 (“I am able to control my self under pressure”, “I always exchange ideas with co-workers about work”, “I always take the time to find the latest information on various things.”), IPMA result is beneficial to assess the most important indicators for employees in shaping job performance through employee perception.

This study examines the influence of team building, employee empowerment, and employee self-efficacy, with the influence of organizational learning culture to drive employee competence and further to innovation and job performance. The results of the PLS-SEM analysis can be described as a result model as follows, where the dashed lines represent hypotheses that are not supported.

Figure 4. Empirical Model

Based on the coefficient value, the strongest predictor to the employees competencies is team building followed by employee self-efficacy. Eventually, the existence of an organizational learning culture is not proven to strengthen the influence of team building and employee empowerment to employee competencies. The organizational learning culture in this study is only proven to strengthen employee self-efficacy in shaping employee competencies. The higher the degree of the learning culture in the organization, the higher the effect of the team building toward employee competencies.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the influence of team building, employee empowerment, and employee self-efficacy, along with organizational learning culture as moderator, convert to employee competencies toward the innovation and performance outcome. This study confirm the theory stated the importance of employee competencies to drive company performance (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). This study revealed, team building is the strongest predictor, therefore should be take into account in HR strategy in order to develop employee competency. The second strong predictor is employee self-efficacy. This finding may associated to the profile of respondents who already have a high tenure, middle to upper position in the company structure, and from the companies that have very low employee turnover. The implication could be drawn, that companies must prioritize team building while pay attention to the need of employee associated by the level of their self-efficacy. The managerial suggestion is that companies must prioritize the team building facilitated by the training and coaching needed by employees.

The results of this study in the context of manufacturing company are in line with research from Ubeda, Santos, and Nagano, (2017) where employee competencies is proven to contribute to the innovation in a company. Since a company's innovation capability is embedded in its workforce, qualified employees are considered a resource for innovation; without this, companies hardly achieve the innovation. The results of this study are also in line with research from Atan and Mahmood's (2019) where employee competence has been shown to have a positive effect on work performance. This study consistent to the result of research by Sabuhari, et al., (2020) that employee competence has a strong significant effect on work performance. Likewise, the results of this study demonstrated that employee competencies proven has significant impact both on innovation and job performance. The application of this research can be useful for the practice of HR department, it is necessity to improve the things that are considered important by employees in improving the quality of their competencies, such as: starting to care and stimulate each employee to be able to control themselves when working underpressure, fostering employee to be more able to exchange ideas with colleagues about work, and pursue open mindset to the environment change.

Team bulding has strong effect toward employee competence, this finding align with previous study from Potnuru et al., (2019) pointed that team building and empowerment are two factors that positively influence employee competence. This study result consistent with the previous study on self-efficacy (Rahim et al., 2019) and thereby offers insight that self-efficacy should be take into account to manage employee competencies in manufacturing company. Consequently, companies must aware the employees need for their self growth to the fullest of their potential. Self-efficacy is vary based on employee potential and experience, therefore company should asses this level accordingly. Recent studies present employee competencies as a possibility to develop individual competencies in companies with more flexible and participatory work structures, well-defined and wide spread organizational values, and a focus on organizational learning

culture (Bitencourt, 2004; Fleury, 2004). This finding is not consistent with the results of previous studies (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009; Zumrah et al., 2013) which determined that organizational support for learning culture has a positive effect on employee skills. However, offer the new insight that learning culture may not generally implied in the different level of employee, while support the posited that learning organization should be dynamic according to employee level (Senge, 1991).

It was found that the role of organizational learning culture was only proven significant to strengthen self-efficacy relation to employee competencies. Surprisingly the OLC found has negative effect, therefore it weakens the relation from employee empowerment to competency. This result may be related to the respondent's profile which are from managerial level that tend to perceive the empowerment by the company mostly work for the operator or frontliner level, while in contrary they more affected by the intrinsic motivation. The high self-efficacy degree of the respondents may be inversely related to that condition. To analyze this phenomenon the dimensionality of learning organization as suggested by Marsick and Watkins (2003) could be done in the future. Implication drawn is that organizational learning culture should attached in program that increase competencis by assessing individual potential such as their character, and motivation. Moreover, the appraisal of employees with high self-efficacy and employees with low efficacy may needed to apply in the organization structure. Training and coaching programs should be well design in accordance with employee self-efficacy and other intrinsic factor. Hence, it can be said that OLC plays an important role as long its match with the employee individual perception of their ability.

The predictive ability of the employee competencies model is slightly close to 0.75, hence it could be categorized as a strong predictive accuracy. In that regard this model is considered adequate to predict employee competencies. Therefore, this model could be replicated in other studies with different populations and industry. On the other hand, the innovation and performance outcome are relatively weak due to single path that predicts each outcome (R^2), however refer to the f^2 value grater than 0,35 this could be conclude has as large effect (Sarsted et al., 2019). In the future, this model could be developed with additional variables to predict innovation and job performance out come accordingly.

CONCLUSION, LIMITATION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

Result of this study demonstrated the positive influence of the team building, employee empowerment, and self-efficacy toward the innovation and job performance mediated by employee competencies in the context of manufacturing company. The OLC play significant role to strengthen the relation of self-efficacy to employee competencies but not did not appear to support in team work and empowerment in this case. Employee compentencis has significant role to drive company outcome, therefore this finding underlined the importance of competencies approach in an organization to achieve innovation and maximum job performance. The challenge which occurs to the manufacturing company during Covid-19 pandemic and beyond, need to be addressed by aligning the team work, empowerment practice and the potential of the employees to improve their competencies in the HR strategy. Moreover, organizational learning culture should be managed properly by consider the individual potential to ensure the positive effect to the employee competencies.

This study has several limitations eventhough it paves the way for other research in the future regarding the HR approaches in employee. Data collected at one point in time (cross-sectional study) and ignore fluctuation of workload in the production period. This may cause problems related to the employee perception toward company policy, therefore it is suggested that future researchers carry out longitudinal study to measure the perception over the time. The data of this research collected only from two companies, eventhough in the same size but these two organizations may not have the same OLC level and style. In that regard for the further research, more companies should be included with the tight criterias that categorize the similar level of OLC. The sample used does not involve employees of operators and other divisions. Hence, it may have limitation to oversee the competence of whole employees in manufacturing company, in that regard future study may include the employees at the operator level and clerck. Lastly, there is a limitation found in the model prediction value to describe innovation and job performance. There are other factors could be deployed in order to explore more complex model to predict innovation performance of the employee such as job engagement. Employee engagement may create a strong binding between organization and its employee that provide the better field in company to keep innovate.

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